

THE ROLE OF GABA-PRODUCING *LACTOBACILLUS* AND *BIFIDOBACTERIUM* IN AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDERS

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Abstract. Autism spectrum disorders (ASD) are complex neurodevelopmental conditions marked by social communication deficits and repetitive behaviors. Recent research highlights the role of gut microbiota, particularly GABA-producing *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* species, in modulating brain function via the gut-brain axis. GABA, the primary inhibitory neurotransmitter in the CNS, helps maintain excitatory/inhibitory (E/I) balance. Dysregulation of GABAergic signaling is linked to ASD symptoms such as anxiety, sensory sensitivity, and social deficits. Preclinical studies suggest that GABA or GABA-producing probiotics can improve these symptoms, especially when combined with glutamatergic modulation. Psychobiotics—probiotics with neuroactive potential—have shown promising effects in reducing anxiety and enhancing social behavior. Some clinical data also indicate moderate benefits in children with ASD. However, further research is required to validate their efficacy, standardize strains, and integrate them into comprehensive ASD treatment strategies.

Keywords: GABA (Gamma-Aminobutyric Acid), *Lactobacillus*, *Bifidobacterium*, gut-brain axis, GABAergic Signaling, psychobiotics, neurodevelopmental disorders, social behavior.

Introduction

Autism spectrum disorders (ASD) are complex neurodevelopmental conditions characterized by social communication deficits and repetitive behaviors. Recent studies emphasize the role of gut microbiota, particularly GABA-producing *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* strains, in influencing brain function via the gut-brain axis. GABA, the main inhibitory neurotransmitter in the central nervous system, plays a key role in maintaining the excitatory/inhibitory (E/I) balance. Disruption of GABAergic signaling is associated with core ASD symptoms, including anxiety and impaired social behavior. Preclinical findings suggest that enhancing GABA transmission—directly or through GABA-producing probiotics—may alleviate these symptoms, especially when combined with glutamatergic modulation [1].

Psychobiotics, or next-generation probiotics with neuroactive properties, have demonstrated anxiolytic and pro-social effects in animal models. Some clinical studies show moderate benefits in children with ASD. However, further research is needed to confirm their efficacy, ensure safety, and establish their role within multimodal treatment approaches.

GABA and Its Role in Neurophysiology

Gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) is the primary inhibitory neurotransmitter in the central nervous system (CNS) of mammals, playing a crucial role in regulating neuronal excitability. Dysfunction of the GABAergic system is considered one of the potential mechanisms underlying the pathogenesis of autism spectrum disorders (ASD), associated with an imbalance between excitatory and inhibitory signals in the brain. Disruptions in GABA metabolism may contribute to increased sensory sensitivity, anxiety disorders, and impaired social adaptation. The

imbalance between excitatory and inhibitory neurotransmitters is recognized as an etiological factor in the development of ASD [2].

GABA's inhibitory action is essential for the regulation of signal transmission and brain development. It has attracted significant attention in studies of the etiology of various neurological disorders such as schizophrenia, depression, and anxiety [3; 4]. Experimental studies have also shown that core ASD symptoms are closely related to impairments in GABAergic signaling [5]. Accumulated data indicate that the sodium-potassium-chloride cotransporter 1 (NKCC1) and the potassium-chloride cotransporter 2 (KCC2) are crucial for proper GABAergic function [6]. NKCC1, a chloride importer, and KCC2, a chloride exporter, are critical components of GABA receptor functioning [7].

GABA Supplementation and Its Effects

GABA supplementation led to moderate improvements in neurotransmitter balance and oxidative stress markers. Biochemically, increased GABA levels were associated with a slight reduction in glutamate levels and a better excitatory/inhibitory (E/I) balance. Restoration of GABAergic transmission helped reduce glutamate-induced excitotoxicity, though the improvements were modest compared to those achieved with combined therapy.

GABA also slightly increased expression of the **GABRA5** gene, enhancing inhibitory neurotransmission. However, this effect was insufficient to fully normalize glutamate levels and oxidative stress in rats exposed to propionic acid (PPA). Behaviorally, GABA-treated rats showed improved social interactions compared to the PPA group, suggesting that enhancing GABAergic transmission can partially mitigate social deficits associated with autism spectrum disorders (ASD). These findings align with other studies highlighting the key role of GABAergic dysfunction in ASD-related social impairments [8].

The moderate improvements observed emphasize the need for more comprehensive therapeutic approaches targeting both GABAergic and glutamatergic systems. For instance, studies using GABA agonists such as **baclofen** have shown that these drugs can significantly reduce symptoms like hyperactivity, impaired social interaction, and spatial memory deficits in genetically modified mouse models. In mice with disrupted excitatory/inhibitory (E/I) balance, **GABA_B receptor agonists** like **arbaclofen** have demonstrated the ability to restore E/I balance and improve behavioral outcomes [9].

Social interaction in treated animals was almost fully restored to normal levels, and immobility was significantly reduced, indicating improvements in anxiety-related behavior. From a histopathological perspective, combined therapy provided marked neuroprotection, effectively eliminating the neurodegenerative changes typically observed in the hippocampus of rats exposed to propionic acid (PPA). It has been shown that multi-component approaches targeting both glutamate-mediated excitotoxicity and excitatory/inhibitory (E/I) imbalance can lead to significant behavioral recovery and preservation of neuronal integrity in ASD models. Oral administration of GABA demonstrated effects on the brain, as evidenced by changes in electroencephalographic (EEG) patterns and improvements in cognitive function [10]. These findings are supported by studies showing that treatment with the probiotic *Lactobacillus reuteri* reduced repetitive behaviors and increased expression of GABA receptor genes (GABRA1, GABRA3, and GABRB1), as well as GABRA1 protein levels in the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex of *Shank3* mutant mice—an established autism model [11].

Earlier, Bravo et al. (2011) also demonstrated that treatment with *Lactobacillus* probiotics affects emotional behavior and the expression of central GABA receptors via the vagus nerve,

which connects the brain and the gut. This highlights the potential of probiotics in modulating the gut–brain axis for the treatment of ASD [12]. Moreover, probiotics that enhance inhibitory neurotransmission by increasing GABA levels and receptor expression may help restore the disrupted excitatory/inhibitory (E/I) balance often observed in ASD. In addition, it contributes to the normalization of PPA-induced elevations in transcripts of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) in the hippocampus, thereby supporting neuroplasticity and the recovery of cognitive functions [13].

The Gut–Brain Axis and the Microbiota

The concept of the "gut–brain axis" refers to the bidirectional communication between the gastrointestinal (GI) tract and the central nervous system (CNS), mediated through neuroimmune, neuroendocrine, and metabolic mechanisms. The gut microbiota influences brain development and function, in part through the production of neurotransmitters and modulation of vagus nerve activity. Among the neuroactive metabolites produced by the microbiota, gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) is of particular importance. Its synthesis is carried out by certain strains of *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium*. The gut microbiota represents a highly organized community of microorganisms inhabiting the human and animal GI tract. Most of the microbial population is localized in the large intestine, with smaller amounts in the stomach and small intestine. Symbiotic relationships between the microbiota and the host develop throughout life—starting at birth and possibly even in utero [14].

The mechanism by which psychobiotics exert their beneficial effects is thought to involve the regulation of neurotransmitters such as serotonin, gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), as well as short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) and enteroendocrine hormones [15].

Psychobiotics have also been shown to influence inflammatory pathways by normalizing levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines and increasing the production of anti-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-10 (IL-10). In addition to their anti-inflammatory effects, psychobiotics can reduce activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis in response to stress [16]. Over the past decade, interest in psychobiotics has grown significantly, leading to substantial progress in understanding their therapeutic potential for disorders associated with the microbiota–gut–brain axis (MGBA). This bidirectional communication between the brain and gut microbiota is thought to occur primarily through the enteric nervous system, the HPA axis, and both central and peripheral nervous systems, involving immune, endocrine, and molecular mechanisms [17].

GABA-Producing Probiotics and ASD

Psychobiotics—next-generation probiotics (NGPs) for the brain—represent a special class of probiotics that positively affect neurological function and may be used in the treatment of mental disorders [15]. Unlike conventional probiotics, psychobiotics act on the gut–brain axis by modulating the microbial composition, activating the immune system, transmitting signals via the vagus nerve, and producing neuroactive metabolites such as neurotransmitters, cytokines, short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), and enteroendocrine hormones. Given this potential, psychobiotics are being widely explored—from reducing stress levels to serving as adjunctive therapy in the treatment of various neurodevelopmental and neurodegenerative disorders, including ADHD, autism spectrum disorder (ASD), Parkinson’s disease, and Alzheimer’s disease [18].

Representatives of the genera *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* are among the most extensively studied probiotics. Strains such as *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, *L. plantarum*,

Bifidobacterium longum, and others have the ability to synthesize GABA through glutamate metabolism via the enzyme glutamate decarboxylase (GAD). Preclinical studies in animal models have shown that administration of GABA-producing probiotics is associated with reduced anxiety, improved social behavior, and normalized behavioral responses.

Individuals with ASD often exhibit gut dysbiosis, characterized by reduced beneficial microbes and an overrepresentation of opportunistic pathogens. Some clinical studies involving children with ASD have indicated that probiotic therapy using GABA-producing strains may improve sleep quality, reduce anxiety, and have a moderately positive effect on communication skills. However, the results remain inconsistent and require validation through randomized, placebo-controlled trials involving larger patient cohorts.

Conclusion

Thus, the gut microbiota—particularly GABA-producing probiotic strains of *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium*—represents a promising component in the pathogenetic and adjunctive treatment of autism spectrum disorders (ASD). Their ability to modulate the gut–brain axis and influence neurotransmitter balance highlights their high potential for future clinical application. However, at the current stage of scientific development, probiotics cannot yet be considered a standalone therapeutic option. Further fundamental and clinical research is needed to standardize probiotic strains, assess their safety and efficacy, and determine optimal treatment protocols as part of a multimodal approach to ASD therapy.

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